

A MACHINE LEARNING FRAMEWORK FOR SOLVING COMPLEX HEALTHCARE PROBLEMS AND FORECASTING CLINICAL OUTCOMES

P. Ramadevi

Research Scholar
University of Technology
Jaipur.

Dr. Suneel Pappala

Research Supervisor
University of Technology
Jaipur.

Dr. R.Nagaraju

Research Co-Supervisor
University of Technology
Jaipur.

ABSTRACT

Healthcare prediction has been a significant factor in saving lives in recent years. In the domain of health care, there is a rapid development of intelligent systems for analysing complicated data relationships and transforming them into real information for use in the prediction process. Consequently, artificial intelligence is rapidly transforming the healthcare industry, and thus comes the role of systems depending on machine learning and deep learning in the creation of steps that diagnose and predict diseases, whether from clinical data or based on images, that provide tremendous clinical support by simulating human perception and can even diagnose diseases that are difficult to detect by human intelligence. Predictive analytics for healthcare a critical imperative in the healthcare industry. Rapid AI advancements can revolutionize healthcare by integrating it into clinical practice. Reporting AI's role in clinical practice is crucial for successful implementation by equipping healthcare providers with essential knowledge and tools. It also discusses the associated challenges, covering ethical and legal considerations and the need for human expertise. By doing so, it enhances understanding of AI's significance in healthcare and supports healthcare organizations in effectively adopting AI technologies. AI tools can leverage large datasets and identify patterns to surpass human performance in several healthcare aspects. AI offers increased accuracy, reduced costs, and time savings while minimizing human errors.

Keywords:Healthcare prediction,machine learning, AI technologies,artificial intelligence,reduced costs.

INTRODUCTION

The application of machine learning dates back to the 1950s when Alan Turing proposed the first machine that can learn and become artificially intelligent. Since its advent, machine learning has been used in various applications, ranging from security services through face detection to increasing efficiency and decreasing risk in public transportation and recently in various aspects of healthcare and biotechnology. Artificial intelligence and machine learning have brought significant changes in business processes and have transformed day-to-day lives, and comparable transformations are anticipated in healthcare and medicine. Recent advancements in this area have displayed incredible progress and opportunity to disburden physicians and improve accuracy, prediction, and quality of care. Current machine learning advancements in healthcare have primarily served as a supportive role in a physician or analyst's ability to fulfill their roles, identify healthcare trends, and develop disease prediction models. In large medical organizations, machine learning-based approaches have also been implemented to achieve increased efficiency in the organization of electronic health records, identification of irregularities in the blood samples, organs, and bones using medical imaging

and monitoring, as well as in robot-assisted surgeries. The advent of widespread electronic health record (EHR) implementation coincided with healthcare advances that rapidly increased the volume and complexity of information clinicians can access about individual patients. Yet, from a clinical data synthesis perspective, the EHR and other electronic sources of clinical information still hold a wealth of untapped information that can benefit overall patient care. Unlocking the promise of electronically-stored healthcare data to improve healthcare across a population of patients requires better development and application of tools that collect and synthesize digitally stored data.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Peter Vanberkel (2023) Machine learning is a powerful tool that can be used to solve a wide range of problems in various applications and industries. The healthcare sector has faced specific challenges that have kept machine learning algorithms from becoming as widely and quickly adopted as in other industries. Data access and management challenges, ethical considerations, safety, and physician and patient perception present bigger barriers to implementation than model performance. In this paper, we propose adapting and customizing the concept of preconditions and postconditions from software engineering to develop a framework based on required clinical parameters and expected clinical output that will help bridge identified gaps in the implementation of machine learning tools in health care.

Xiaoliang Wang (2022) We present a general framework for developing a machine learning (ML) tool that supports clinician assessment of patient risk using electronic health record-derived real-world data and apply the framework to a quality improvement use case in an oncology setting to identify patients at risk for a near-term (60 day) emergency department (ED) visit who could potentially be eligible for a home-based acute care program. Framework steps include defining clinical quality improvement goals, model development and validation, bias assessment, retrospective and prospective validation, and deployment in clinical workflow. In the prospective analysis, 10% of patients were classified as high risk, 76% of whom were confirmed by clinicians as eligible for home-based acute care. PPV and NPV for future ED events was 22% and 95%, respectively. OR of ED visit (high- vs. low-risk) was 5.4 (95% CI: 2.6–11.0). The proposed framework for an ML-based tool that supports clinician assessment of patient risk is a stepwise development approach; we successfully applied the framework to an ED visit risk prediction use case.

Abid Haleem (2022) Machine Learning (ML) applications are making a considerable impact on healthcare. ML is a subtype of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technology that aims to improve the speed and accuracy of physicians' work. Countries are currently dealing with an overburdened healthcare system with a shortage of skilled physicians, where AI provides a big hope. The healthcare data can be used gainfully to identify the optimal trial sample, collect more data points, assess ongoing data from trial participants, and eliminate data-based errors. ML-based techniques assist in detecting early indicators of an epidemic or pandemic. This algorithm examines satellite data, news and social media reports, and even video sources to determine whether the sickness will become out of control. Using ML for healthcare can open up a world of possibilities in this field. It frees up healthcare providers' time to focus on patient care rather than searching or entering information. This study studies ML and its need in healthcare, and then it discusses the associated features and appropriate pillars of ML for healthcare structure. Finally, it identified and discussed the significant applications of ML for

healthcare. The applications of this technology in healthcare operations can be tremendously advantageous to the organisation. ML-based tools are used to provide various treatment alternatives and individualised treatments and improve the overall efficiency of hospitals and healthcare systems while lowering the cost of care.

Hafsa Habehh (2021)Recent advancements in Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) technology have brought on substantial strides in predicting and identifying health emergencies, disease populations, and disease state and immune response, amongst a few. Although, skepticism remains regarding the practical application and interpretation of results from ML-based approaches in healthcare settings, the inclusion of these approaches is increasing at a rapid pace. Here we provide a brief overview of machine learning-based approaches and learning algorithms including supervised, unsupervised, and reinforcement learning along with examples. Second, we discuss the application of ML in several healthcare fields, including radiology, genetics, electronic health records, and neuroimaging. We also briefly discuss the risks and challenges of ML application to healthcare such as system privacy and ethical concerns and provide suggestions for future applications.

Aakansha Gupta (2020)Real-time surveillance in the field of health informatics has emerged as a growing domain of interest among worldwide researchers. Evolution in this field has helped in the introduction of various initiatives related to public health informatics. Surveillance systems in the area of health informatics utilizing social media information have been developed for early prediction of disease outbreaks and to monitor diseases. In the past few years, the availability of social media data, particularly Twitter data, enabled real-time syndromic surveillance that provides immediate analysis and instant feedback to those who are charged with follow-ups and investigation of potential outbreaks. In this study, we review the recent work, trends, and machine learning (ML) text classification approaches used by surveillance systems seeking social media data in the healthcare domain. We also highlight the limitations and challenges followed by possible future directions that can be taken further in this domain. To study the landscape of research in health informatics performing surveillance of the various health related data posted on social media or web-based platforms, we present a bibliometric analysis of the 1240 publications indexed in multiple scientific databases from the year 2010–2018.

Renato Umeton (2020)This work aims to provide a review of the existing literature in the field of automated machine learning (AutoML) to help healthcare professionals better utilize machine learning models “off-the-shelf” with limited data science expertise. We also identify the potential opportunities and barriers to using AutoML in healthcare, as well as existing applications of AutoML in healthcare. Methods: Published papers, accompanied with code, describing work in the field of AutoML from both a computer science perspective or a biomedical informatics perspective were reviewed. We also provide a short summary of a series of AutoML challenges hosted by ChaLearn. A review of 101 papers in the field of AutoML revealed that these automated techniques can match or improve upon expert human performance in certain machine learning tasks, often in a shorter amount of time. The main limitation of AutoML at this point is the ability to get these systems to work efficiently on a large scale, i.e. beyond small- and medium-size retrospective datasets. The utilization of machine learning techniques has the demonstrated potential to improve health outcomes, cut healthcare costs, and advance clinical research. However, most hospitals are not currently

deploying machine learning solutions. One reason for this is that health care professionals often lack the machine learning expertise that is necessary to build a successful model, deploy it in production, and integrate it with the clinical workflow.

Mohd Javaid (2020)Healthcare delivery requires the support of new technologies like Artificial Intelligence (AI), Internet of Things (IoT), Big Data and Machine Learning to fight and look ahead against the new diseases. We aim to review the role of AI as a decisive technology to analyse, prepare us for prevention and fight with COVID-19 (Coronavirus) and other pandemics. The rapid review of the literature is done on the database of Pubmed, Scopus and Google Scholar using the keyword of COVID-19 or Coronavirus and Artificial Intelligence or AI. Collected the latest information regarding AI for COVID-19, then analysed the same to identify its possible application for this disease. We have identified seven significant applications of AI for COVID-19 pandemic. This technology plays an important role to detect the cluster of cases and to predict where this virus will affect in future by collecting and analysing all previous data. Healthcare organizations are in an urgent need for decision-making technologies to handle this virus and help them in getting proper suggestions in real-time to avoid its spread. AI works in a proficient way to mimic like human intelligence. It may also play a vital role in understanding and suggesting the development of a vaccine for COVID-19. This result-driven technology is used for proper screening, analysing, prediction and tracking of current patients and likely future patients. The significant applications are applied to tracks data of confirmed, recovered and death cases.

Mohamed Elhoseny (2018)Recently, cloud computing gained an important role in healthcare services (HCS) due to its ability to improve the HCS performance. However, the optimal selection of virtual machines (VMs) to process a medical request represents a big challenge. Optimal selection of VMs performs a significant enhancement of the performance through reducing the execution time of medical requests (tasks) coming from stakeholders (patients, doctors, etc.) and maximizing utilization of cloud resources. For that, this paper proposes a new model for HCS based on cloud environment using Parallel Particle Swarm Optimization (PPSO) to optimize the VMs selection. In addition, a new model for chronic kidney disease (CKD) diagnosis and prediction is proposed to measure the performance of our VMs model. The prediction model of CKD is implemented using two consecutive techniques, which are linear regression (LR) and neural network (NN). LR is used to determine critical factors that influence on CKD. NN is used to predict of CKD. The results show that, the proposed model outperforms the state-of-the art models in total execution time the rate of 50%. In addition, the system efficiency regarding real-time data retrieval is greatly improved by 5.2%.

Manik Sharma (2018)The study presents a brief introduction to big data and its role in healthcare applications. It is observed that the use of big data architecture and techniques are continuously assisting in managing the expeditious data growth in healthcare industry. Here, initially an empirical study is performed to analyse the role of big data in healthcare industry. It has been observed that significant work has been done using big data in healthcare sector. Nowadays, it is intricate to envision the way the machine learning and big data can influence the healthcare industries. It has been observed that most of the authors who implemented the use of machine learning and big data analytics in disease diagnosis have not given significant weightage to the privacy and security of the data. Here, a novel design of smart and secure

healthcare information system using machine learning and advanced security mechanism has been proposed to handle big data of medical industry. The innovation lies in the incorporation of optimal storage and data security layer used to maintain security and privacy. Different techniques like masking encryption, activity monitoring, granular access control, dynamic data encryption and end point validation have been incorporated. The proposed hybrid four-layer healthcare model seems to be more effective disease diagnostic big data system.

Nigam H. Shah (2017) Machine learning applied to electronic health records (EHRs) can generate actionable insights, from improving upon patient risk score systems, to predicting the onset of disease, to streamlining hospital operations. Statistical models that leverage the variety and richness of EHR-derived data are still relatively rare and offer an exciting avenue for further research. In this chapter, we present an overview of how machine learning has been applied in clinical settings and summarize the advantages it offers over traditional analysis methods. We describe the methodological and operational challenges of using machine learning in research and practice. Lastly, we offer our perspective on future application areas for machine learning that will significantly impact health and healthcare delivery.

Overview of Artificial Intelligence

Although the terms machine learning, deep learning, and artificial intelligence are typically used interchangeably, they represent different sets of algorithms and learning processes. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is the umbrella term that refers to any computerized intelligence that learns and imitates human intelligence. AI is most regarded for autonomous machines such as robots and self-driving cars, but it also permeates everyday applications, such as personalized advertisements and web searches. In recent years, AI development and application have made incredible strides and have been applied to many areas due to their higher levels of decision-making, accuracy, problem-solving capability, and computational skills. In general all development of AI algorithms, the data obtained is split into two groups, a training and test data set, to ensure reliable learning, representative populations, and unbiased predictions. As the name suggests, the training set is used for algorithm training that includes sets of characterizing data points (features) and corresponding predictions (in the case of supervised learning). The testing data set is new to the algorithm and is solely used to test the algorithm's abilities. This measure is taken to eliminate biases in the algorithm's testing by the training dataset. Once an algorithm passes through a training and testing phase with acceptable results, the algorithms are implemented in healthcare settings.

Types of Learning Approaches

Most of the machine learning and AI-based algorithms are built on different learning approaches. One subtype is supervised learning, which is used in training classification and prediction algorithms based on previous examples, or outputs. An important distinction for this learning technique is that the training set involves features and corresponding predictions, or outcomes. Simply put, the supervised learning approach generalizes information from the training set's features to construct a model that can correctly predict training-set outcomes and then uses the learned model to make predictions using the new features in the testing data set. Decision Trees, Random Forest, Support Vector Machines, and Artificial Neural Networks are a few types of ML algorithms that implement supervised learning approaches. Decision tree algorithms form a decision support tool that begins with a

single node and identifies the possible outcomes of that decision. The tree continues with the product of that decision and the following decisions until it reaches a final product. Support Vector Machines (SVM) are known as classification algorithms that use supervised learning to classify features in two group problems by finding the largest margin hyperplane to separate the data and providing the best fit to organize it. Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) consist of an input layer, one or more hidden layers, and output layers, where functional unities/neurons in one layer are connected to every neuron in the layer before and after. In healthcare, supervised machine learning approaches are widely implemented in disease prediction, identifying hospital outcomes, and image detection to name a few.

Dose optimization and therapeutic drug monitoring

AI plays a crucial role in dose optimization and adverse drug event prediction, offering significant benefits in enhancing patient safety and improving treatment outcomes. By leveraging AI algorithms, healthcare providers can optimize medication dosages tailored to individual patients and predict potential adverse drug events, thereby reducing risks and improving patient care. In a study that aimed to develop an AI-based prediction model for prothrombin time international normalized ratio (PT/INR) and a decision support system for warfarin maintenance dose optimization. The authors analyzed data from 19,719 inpatients across three institutions, and the algorithm outperformed expert physicians with significant differences in predicting future PT/INRs and the generated individualized warfarin dose was reliable. On the contrary, a novel dose optimization system—CURATE.AI—is an AI-derived platform for dynamically optimizing chemotherapy doses based on individual patient data. A study was conducted to validate this system as an open-label, prospective trial in patients with advanced solid tumors treated with three different chemotherapy regimens. CURATE.AI generated personalized doses for subsequent cycles based on the correlation between chemotherapy dose variation and tumor marker readouts. The integration of CURATE.AI into the clinical workflow showed successful incorporation and potential benefits in terms of reducing chemotherapy dose and improving patient response rates and durations compared to the standard of care. These findings support the need for prospective validation through randomized clinical trials and indicate the potential of AI in optimizing chemotherapy dosing and lowering the risk of adverse drug events.

AI in drug information and consultation

AI would propose a new support system to assist practical decision-making tools for healthcare providers. In recent years, healthcare institutions have provided a greater leveraging capacity of utilizing automation-enabled technologies to boost workflow effectiveness and reduce costs while promoting patient safety, accuracy, and efficiency. By introducing advanced technologies like NLP, ML, and data analytics, AI can significantly provide real-time, accurate, and up-to-date information for practitioners at the hospital. According to the McKinsey Global Institute, ML and AI in the pharmaceutical sector have the potential to contribute approximately \$100 billion annually to the US healthcare system. Researchers claim that these technologies enhance decision-making, maximize creativity, increase the effectiveness of research and clinical trials, and produce new tools that benefit healthcare providers, patients, insurers, and regulators. AI enables quick and comprehensive retrieval of drug-related information from different resources through its ability to analyse the current medical literature, drug databases, and clinical guidelines to provide accurate and

evidence-based decisions for healthcare providers. Using automated response systems, AI-powered virtual assistants can handle common questions and provide detailed medical information to healthcare providers. AI-powered chatbots help reduce the workload on healthcare providers, allowing them to focus on more complicated cases that require their expertise.

AI virtual healthcare assistance

With continuously increasing demands of health care services and limited resources worldwide, finding solutions to overcome these challenges is essential. Virtual health assistants are a new and innovative technology transforming the healthcare industry to support healthcare professionals. It is designed to simulate human conversation to offer personalized patient care based on input from the patient. These digital assistants use AI-powered applications, chatbots, sounds, and interfaces. Virtual assistants can help patients with tasks such as identifying the underlying problem based on the patient's symptoms, providing medical advice, reminding patients to take their medications, scheduling doctor appointments, and monitoring vital signs. In addition, digital assistants can collect information daily regarding patients' health and forward the reports to the assigned physician. By taking off some of these responsibilities from human healthcare providers, virtual assistants can help to reduce their workload and improve patient outcomes. Furthermore, these tools can always be available, making it easier for patients to access healthcare when needed. Another medical service that an AI-driven phone application can provide is triaging patients and finding out how urgent their problem is, based on the entered symptoms into the app. The National Health Service (NHS) has tested this app in north London, and now about 1.2 million people are using this AI chatbot to answer their questions instead of calling the NHS non-emergency number. In addition, introducing intelligent speakers into the market has a significant benefit in the lives of elderly and chronically ill patients who are unable to use smartphone apps efficiently.

CONCLUSION

While the overview demonstrates how much progress has been achieved with machine learning, there continues to be potential for widescale advancement in the future. Many of the current machine learning advancements in healthcare aim to support the physician's or specialist's ability to provide a more effective treatment to patients with increased quality, speed, and precision. The challenges of developing ML algorithms can be solved by developing and implementing improvements in data collection, storage, and dissemination or by creating algorithms to process unstructured data to address the lack of data availability. Future applications can also bring forth inexpensive forms of medical imaging and affordable medical examinations, potentially ending health disparities and creating more accessible services for countries and lower-income populations. Scientists expect advancement in the prediction of personalized drug response, optimization of medication selection and dosage, and an application of genetic modification to provide treatment for genetic disorders and mutations. With its application, ML can augment the role of physicians and redefine patient care. While the risks and challenges of the future application are addressed and corrected, the current ML algorithms can provide an excellent framework for future advancements and applications of ML in healthcare.

REFERENCES

1. Hafsa Habebh (2021), "Machine Learning in Healthcare", *Curr Genomics.*, issn: 1875-5488, vol. 22(4), pages. 291-300.[doi: 10.2174/1389202922666210705124359](https://doi.org/10.2174/1389202922666210705124359)
2. Xiaoliang Wang (2022), "A machine learning framework supporting prospective clinical decisions applied to risk prediction in oncology", *npj Digital Medicine*, issn: 2398-6352, vol. 5,<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-022-00660-3>
3. Peter Vanberkel (2023), "A framework for implementing machine learning in healthcare based on the concepts of preconditions and postconditions", *Healthcare Analytics*, issn: 2772-4425, vol. 3,<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.health.2023.100155>
4. Abid Haleem (2022), "Significance of machine learning in healthcare: Features, pillars and applications", *International Journal of Intelligent Networks*, issn: 2666-6030, vol. 3, pages. 58-73.<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijin.2022.05.002>
5. Mohamed Elhoseny (2018), "A machine learning model for improving healthcare services on cloud computing environment", *Measurement*, issn: 1873-412X, vol. 119, pages. 117-128.<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2018.01.022>
6. Manik Sharma (2018), "Big Data and Machine Learning Based Secure Healthcare Framework", *Procedia Computer Science*, issn: 1877-0509, vol. 132, pages. 1049-1059.[doi:10.1016/j.procs.2018.05.020](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2018.05.020)
7. Aakansha Gupta (2020), "Social media based surveillance systems for healthcare using machine learning: A systematic review", *Journal of Biomedical Informatics*, issn: 1532-0480, vol. 108,<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbi.2020.103500>
8. Renato Umeton (2020), "Automated machine learning: Review of the state-of-the-art and opportunities for healthcare", *Artificial Intelligence In Medicine*, issn: 1873-2860, vol. 104,<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.artmed.2020.101822>
9. Nigam H. Shah (2017), "Chapter 19 - Machine Learning in Healthcare", *Key Advances in Clinical Informatics*, isbn: 9780128095232, pages. 279-291.<https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-809523-2.00019-4>
10. Mohd Javaid (2020), "Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications for COVID-19 pandemic", *Diabetes & Metabolic Syndrome: Clinical Research & Reviews*, issn: 1878-0334, vol. 14, pages. 337-339.<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dsx.2020.04.012>